

MANAGING VIRAL ATTACK IN COMPUTER SYSTEMS

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Abstract

In order to understand the global virus spread, a system is either infected or not. If the system is infected, there is a possibility each day that it will have an infectious contact with some other systems in the network via exchange of floppy disk or software over the network of computers. Similarly, there is some other possibility each day that an infected system is discovered to be infected which is cleaned up and returned to the pool of uninfected computers. The integral number of time period past the moment when the process is started represents the states of the process which may be finite or infinite.

The main aim of this work is to examine various ways of contacting or copying viral codes, their reproduction cycle and the preventive measures when computers are attacked by a virus. Also is to study why people write viral codes and give the economic consequences of viruses to organizations, so that they will be guided to controlling the spread of viruses.

The work will be a useful guide to University researchers and research institutions in the creation and control of viruses so that policy makers can enact laws for the management and control of viruses

Keywords: *Managing, Viral attack, Computer systems.*

Introduction

Computer Viruses

A computer virus is a self replicating piece of computer code (instructions) that can partially or fully attach itself to files or applications and cause the computer to do what it was not originally intended to do (John and

Heyness, 2002). It is therefore a program that requires a host in order to make copies of itself on a computer disk. They are small programs that attach themselves to computer applications and wreck havoc on a computer system. They are spread when infected files are transferred from one computer to another. Some viruses actively destroy software or entire computer system and render them unusable, some can delete files, some open up a doorway to let hackers into a network undetected, some can be used to initiate denial of service, some cause texts or graphics to be displayed where they are not wanted, some slow down a computer's communications and processing capabilities, while some just reside there and don't do much of anything. They can cause significant economic damage (Peter, 2008).

The ability to self replicate distinguishes viruses from programs that do not. All viruses are created by people who write computer program in assembly language. The parasitic nature of viruses is neither an accident nor a computer malfunction. The essential feature of a computer program that causes it to be classified as a virus is not its ability to destroy data, but its ability to gain control of computer and make fully functional copy of itself. It can reproduce and those copies may later be executed to create still more copies. The computer virus overcome the road block of operator control by hiding itself in other programs, thus, it gains access to the C. P. U. simply because users run programs that it happens to attach itself to without their knowledge (Phillips, Peter and Martin 2006). A computer virus is thus a code that attaches itself to other programs in order to alter their behavior often in a harmful way. A virus writer can set the payload to trigger immediately, at a preset future time or data or upon the execution of a specified command such as SAVE or OPEN a file

Historical Development of Computer Viruses and Worms

It is convenient to define computer crime as any criminal act which involves one or more computers as an object of crime or as accessories in its commission. Computer crime can be divided into Computer Related Crime (C. R. C) and Computer Assisted Crime (C. A. C.). In the former, the computer or its contents is the subject of the criminal act e.g. hackers or denial of service attack, while in the latter, computer is merely an accessory in the commission of the crime which could have been committed by other means e.g. financial fraud or embezzlement. (Richard , 2009).

In 1972 according to Richard, 2009, Spoke Dan Edward coined the term Trojan horse after the GREEKS ingenious scheme to end the siege of TROY. It denotes an apparently benign macro or utility with undocumented side effects which may be security violation or destructive. A Trojan horse denotes a backdoor or security loophole left in a system which can be explored for access purposes. In 1982, John Shoch and John Hopp from the RANKXERROX PALO RESEARCH centre (XR – PARC) reported the first experiments with worm programs. The aim of their work was to MOP – UP the idle time on a network of computers with useful computations in a manner transparent to the users. The worm program replicated itself in each node of the network and activates a portion of the desired computation if the node is quiescent (if the node becomes busy its computation is suspended and withdrawn). The first computer virus program was written as an experiment by FRED COHEN, in November 1988 whilst a graduate student at the University of Southern California. As distinct from worms, viruses are parasitic replicators which must attach themselves to other machine instructions in order to be executed by the processor. The first virus infection in the wild, by the BRAIN virus from Pakistan was recorded in 1986.

Basic hacking or unauthorized access, has been practiced by students, computer technophiles, commercial spies and intelligent services. Their

motivation includes recreation, intellectual curiosity, technical challenge, freedom of information, demonstrating security flaws, gaining commercial advantage and national security. To enter a system, either an existing trapdoor must be explored or a valid password must be found. Passwords may be obtained by social engineering or locally by shoulder surfing that may be guessed or systematically cracked or discovered using password grabber or packet sniffer programs (Richard, 2009). Software bombs have a similar role of destructive Trojan planted (usually well concealed) within some mission critical software that consist of a trigger and a payload. If the trigger is a date or time, it is termed a time bomb, whereas if the trigger is a logical condition, it is termed logical bomb. When the host application is run, the trigger condition is tested and if it is time, then the payload is activated with destructive consequences. It can thus be used either for sabotage or for blackmail or extortion (Lance, 2010).

In November 1992, Gareth Harly was convicted of planting a logic bomb at CHILWORTH communications, prior to his resignation in September 1990. One month later, the logic bomb was triggered damaging business critical files at a cost of over three hundred thousand dollars. Yet in December 1992, Hardy was sentenced to 140 hours community service and ordered to pay three thousand dollars compensation. Unlike logic bombs which are concealed, Trojan horses need to be explicitly run by an unwitting user in order to perpetuate their hidden side effects (Mark, 2006). They can be sub divided into those that dupe the user by offering something interesting and those that masquerade as an everyday utility. Worms programs are replicators which do not necessarily damage information but instead of performing useful computation as envisaged, they may simply consume system and network resources. In November 1998, Robert Moris Jr, a student of Cornell University released a worm program which explored trapdoors in the UNIX systems to spread itself through 6,200 computers on the internet

bringing them to a standstill for up to a week at an estimated cost of over 100 million dollars. Worm programs thus have the potential for sabotage, extortion and blackmail. Being parasitic replicators, unlike worms, computer viruses must attach themselves to executable or command files, bootstrap sector of discs or macros with documents (Klim, 2002).

The first author of a virus to be convicted under Computer Misuse Act (CMA 90), was Cristopher Pole (a. k.a. Black Baron) who was sentenced to 18 months imprisonment in November 1996 on 11 count charges including the damage done to Pathogen and Queen. Although the motivation in this case was apparently vandalism, the potential of viruses and related malicious codes for information warfare was also evident. Computer crime is continuing to develop apace, and the price of freedom is eternal vigilance, the existence of CMA90 has not itself stemmed the tide of computer crime, and the potential weakness of the human component of security is still not adequately recognized. Viruses got their names when a University Professor used the term VIRUS to describe them in 1984, because like biological virus (Fred, 2005), a computer virus is small, make copies of itself and do not exist without a host. While most viruses are just annoying and time wasting, the ones that do deliver a destructive payload are a real treat. Widely available internet and E- mail access hastened their spread. In the year 2000, the advent of viruses that spread via e – mail significantly increased the odds that the average computer users would confront a virus because they spread so rapidly. E- mail viruses today can infect thousands of computers in a matter of minutes.

Reasons why People Write virus code

People create viruses. A person has to write the code, test it to make sure it spreads properly before it is released (Klim, 2002). The attack phase of the virus must also be designed whether it is simply a silly message or

destruction of a hard disk, so why do people do it:

- i. The psychology that drove vandals and arsonists: Why would somebody want to rob somebody or kill another person or break the windows of somebody's car? If that person happens to know how to write computer programs, then he/she may turn his energy into creation of destructive viruses.
- ii. The skill of watching things blow up: Many people have a fascination with things like explosives, creating a virus that spreads quickly is like that i.e. create a bomb inside a computer and the more computers that get infected the more the fun of the explosion.
- iii. Bragging rights or a thrill of doing it: If people are certain programmer and they see a hole that could be explored, they might be compelled to exploit the hole themselves before someone else beat them to it.
- iv. Some people may be bored, curious or intent on doing forbidden things just to frighten others.
- v. Some may belong to organized virus writing groups and those in the group respond to peer pressure to outdo each other. Whether in a group or not, some derive satisfaction from the challenge, while others think of themselves as rebels against the system.

Entry points of viruses

In order to establish where antivirus software should be deployed in an organization (Abubakar, 2005), it is important to establish the common entry points of viruses. These include among others

i. E- Mail

The overwhelming large population of infections today is caused by infected E- mail attachments. The ease with which a user can click on an attachment and launch an application is significant factor in the spread of e – mail borne viruses. The danger of infection through attachment is not only confined to

e-mail but also on newsgroups posting that carry attachments too.

II **World Wide Web (WWW)**

The web is full of sites carrying virus materials. Organizations should however, try to provide physically separate PCS to access the web for a much better arrangements. Not only should internet be physically separated from the company's main network but for employees who tend to waste much less time surfing non – work related sites.

III **Floppy Disks, CDS and other Disks**

The use of floppy disks has decreased radically with the advent of networks, but most PCS come with a floppy drive filled as standards. Most infections are due to boot sector viruses, which show that floppy disks are not dead. Many people have become first victims of brand new viruses and worms by downloading executable files that are posted deliberately by vandals

How Viruses Spread

Early viruses were piece of code attached to a common program like a popular game or a word processor. A person might download an infected game from a bulletin board and run it. Any virus is designed to run first when a legitimate program gets executed. The virus loads itself in memory and looks around to see if it can find any other program on the disk to modify it and add virus code to the unsuspecting program (Klim, 2002). Then the virus launches the real program. The user really has no way to know that the virus ever runs. Unfortunately, the virus gets executed, they affect other programs and the cycle continues. If one of the infected programs is given to another person on a disk or if it is uploaded to a bulletin board, the other programs get infected. The spreading part is the infection phase of the virus. Viruses have some sort of destructive attack phase where they do some damage. Some sort of trigger will activate, the attack phase and then the virus will then do something such as anything from printing a silly message on the screen to erasing all the data

in the system. The trigger might be a specific date or a number of times the virus has been replicated. One important trick the virus creators adopt is the ability to load viruses into memory so that they keep on running in the background for as long as the computer remains on (Peter, 2008). This gives viruses much more effective way to replicate themselves. Another trick was the ability to infect the boot sector on disks. The boot sector is a small program that is the first part of the operating system that tells the computer how to load the rest of the operating system. By putting its code in the boot sector, a virus will quarantine it gets executed. It can load itself in memory immediately and able to run whenever the computer is on (Ralf, 2008).

Viruses and worms spread faster among computers networked on Local Area Network (LAN), especially when e – mail file attachments are involved. Riskiest of all are files posted on internet groups because there is no control or accountability. Many people have become the first victims of brand new viruses and worms by downloading executable files that were posted by vandals. Many people may be fortunate never to encounter viruses but vandal programs could be concealed in the next file that is downloaded or a file attachment to an e – mail attachment. In order to spread and avoid detection, computer viruses often defer actions of hostile actions. The existence of computer virus typically involves four actions, dormancy, propagation, triggering and damage (John and Hayness , 2002). Upon infection of a new computer or a program, the computer virus may remain dormant for a while to avert suspicion. A machine usually becomes infected by running contaminated programs. Computer viruses are commonly spread through acquisition of programs directly or indirectly obtained from computer vendors or bulletin boards in form of software or public domain programs. The duration of the dormant period may vary depending on the type of the machine being used. The virus may await a certain number of executions of the host program or the elapsing of a certain period of time before

propagating to the next stage.— propagation. In the propagation stage the virus attempts to infect other programs in the host machine. The target can be the operating system and the boot sector. In order for the virus to spread (Eugene, 2009), the infected carrier program must be executed. The virus spreads by searching the system for infected programs and attaches itself to them. Depending on the mechanism used, the virus code will modify an executable file in such a manner that it receives control upon program activation. When the infected program is executed, the virus code receives control and performs the work appropriate for the stage it is in. Control is then referred to the host program for normal operation. In this way, the virus can hide its existence all the way through the triggering stage (John, 2009).

After completing the self propagation stage, the trigger is activated to facilitate transition to damage stage. The trigger may be defined as a count of replications or it may be time based so as to cause the damage at some specific time or date i.e 6th February of every year or a command such as SAVE. The damage itself can range from the benign form of printing a message, announcing the presence of the virus and the malignant damage such as erasure of files or severing of the boot sector (Jeffrey, Kephart and Sleve, 2005).

How to tell if a Computer System has Virus

- I. Boot failure: If a computer is booted and it fails to boot, it may be due to virus infection
- II. If a user of a computer is typing and some texts being typed start to drop to the bottom of the screen, then it could be due to virus infection
- III. If it is noticed that rectangular blocks or blank spaces have started appearing on the V.D.U. then the computer is already infected with virus
- IV. When typing to save a file on the hard disk or any disk, if it is noticed of a display that the space on the hard disk cannot accommodate what is

intended to be saved and yet one is sure there is enough space to save the file, then suspect virus problem.

Consequence and Economic loss of Virus Attack

- I. Loss of data
- II. Loss of programs
- III. Corruption of data
- IV. Destruction of data
- V. System malfunction or failure to boot
- VI. Waste of money and time to clean up viruses
- VII. Anxiety

Guides against Viruses

- i. Try to educate the people that use the computers about the dangers of viruses
- ii. Access control to the computers. What people come in and go out with from a computer unit should be monitored
- iii. Create CD banks around the computer facilities that are to be used
- iv. Avoid opening unexpected e – mail attachments and downloads from unreliable sources
- v. Resist the urge to double click everything in the mail box
- vi. There is need to install reliable anti – virus scanning software

Cleaning Infected Systems

- I. Validate the infection by using another anti – virus product if possible
- II. Evaluate the damage if any that has been done by the virus infection
- III. Ask for advice or get help from knowledgeable source and not from computer operators on the street or non – computer professionals who claim to be experts and yet they are not.

Minimizing the threat of Virus Infections

- I. Take regular backups of data as the most appropriate precaution the system administrator can take against data loss, whether the data loss is as a result of hardware or software malfunction or virus infection. It is important to ensure that organizations are able to restore data from these backups.
- II. Ensure that all in-coming software come from reputable sources
- III. Write-protects all disks drives whenever possible to prevent virus infection.
- V. Discourage users from leaving disks in the drives of PCS when they are switched off to prevent PCS from being inadvertently booted from a disk infected with boot sector virus

Conclusion

The value of computer system lies in its store of knowledge and its capability to perform tasks. One can always buy a replacement of a system but there is no convenient retail store that can sell to users the data wiped away by virus (Sussan K, 2009). Preventing people from software from writing to disks is only a first step, scanning the disk for virus is the essential next step. People who are interested in how things work have been able to learn a little bit about computer virus. It is truly difficult to deny that they are interesting. The idea of a computer program that can take off and gain a life completely independent of its maker is well exciting. Think of a whole new universe not this physical world, but an electronic one, which exist inside of a computer, there is a virus world, where it can live in a sense not too different from that of primitive biological life (Mark, 2008). The computer virus has the same goal as a living organism – to survive and to produce. It has environmental scales to overcome, what could kill it and render it inoperative. And once it is released, it seems to have a mind of its own. It runs off in its

electronic world doing what it was programmed to do and in this sense it is much alive.

The essential feature of a computer program that causes it to be classified as a virus is not its ability to destroy data but to gain control of the computer system and make a functional copy of itself. When it is executed, it makes one or more copies of itself (Adio, 1999). These copies may later be executed to create more copies, an infinite. It can hop from machine to machine, accomplishing the goals programmed into it, with none to control it. It is important that anti – virus software detect virus that have been observed in the world. We must always be prepared for the possibility that low profile viruses will start to become prevalent (U. S. , Air force (2007). What will be needed is a system which can detect an anomaly in real time, analyze the threat and produce the detection and remove data in hours or minutes, then distribute the data to the original machines as well as other machines that may be in the path of the virus (Phillips, Peter and Martin, 2006). The emerging computer technology, like all new technologies is a two edge sword. Just as biological viruses can cause diseases in humans, computer virus can cause diseases in computer systems, but in a sense, the benefit of biological research on quality of life is indispensable, and benefits of computer virus research may someday pay off in the quality of our information system and by extension our real being. Computer systems are one of the greatest laboratory facilities we have. Their ability to model and mimic life and life – like situations is astounding both in its accuracy and its ability to allow experiments that would be infeasible in any laboratory (Steve, 2002).

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